

**PROGRAM TO INSTITUTIONALIZE MERITOCRACY AND EXCELLENCE IN
HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (PRIME HRM) PRACTICES AND
SCHOOL PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS
IN THE DIVISION OF CALAMBA CITY**

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Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (Prime HRM) Practices and School Performance in Public Elementary Schools in the Division of Calamba City

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Abstract

This descriptive-correlational research assessed the Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME HRM) practices and school performance in public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City. It utilized a standardized questionnaire as the main data-gathering instrument. Total enumeration and proportionate random sampling techniques were applied in the selection of School Head and teacher respondents, respectively from the nine (9) clusters of public elementary schools. The analyzed data revealed that the PRIME HRM practices of recruitment, selection, and placement (4.66); learning and development (4.52); performance management (4.73); and, rewards and recognition (4.47) were fully practiced or always implemented. The findings also revealed that the school access (3.93%) and efficiency in terms of dropout rate (1.30%) were at a marginal level, while the school quality (5.07%) was at an average level. However, the school performance in terms of completion rate (98.96%) and Cohort Survival Rate (98.83%) were both at high levels. The comparative test yielded a significant difference between the School Heads and teachers' assessments of the level of implementation of PRIME HRM Practices. On the other hand, the correlation test generated no significant relationship between the level of implementation of PRIME HRM practices and the level of performance of public elementary schools. The computed probability values were greater than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$). Based on these findings, this research proposed a plan of action to enhance the implementation of PRIME HRM practices in the Division of Calamba City.

Keywords: *human resource, school performance, recruitment and selection, administration, education*

Introduction

Human Resource Management (HRM) was the department inside a business that was responsible for hiring, managing, and giving guidance to its employees. In the dynamic and ever-changing marketplace, gaining a competitive edge and improving organizational performance was largely dependent on the growth and management of an organization's human resources. To inspire and improve organizational performance, human resource management—a crucial component of management—involved the methodical process of recruiting, developing, rewarding, and retaining the company's core employees. Human resource management was used to enhance their abilities (Iguisi & Orakwue, 2020)

In the Philippines, the Civil Service Commission (CSC) creates programs that incorporated expertise in the nation's human resources to fulfill its aim of becoming a Center of Excellence for Organizational Development and Human Resources. PRIME-HRM, or the Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management, was one of the several initiatives run by the CSC. The PRIME-HRM used three steps—Assess, Assist, and Award—to evaluate an agency's HR excellence-oriented systems, processes, and human resource management competencies. The primary objective of the program was to elevate the agency's HRM maturity level from Transactional to Strategic. Staff, teachers, and administration were all included in management. These individuals were led and trained to become effective professionals (Inarda, 2020).

Moreover, public schools in the Philippines were required to adhere to the rules established by the Civil Service Commission (CSC) and were overseen by their own Board of Regents. They continued to encounter significant obstacles in performance management, selection and placement, and recruiting despite CSC's attempts to integrate a variety of HR initiatives. Ten human resource management officers participated in in-depth interviews that were exploratory in character and used the Grounded Theory technique. The findings derived from the qualitative data indicated that organizational value, leadership, management, strategic, and cultural restrictions hindered an HRMO's ability to effectively handle any strategic difficulties. The study suggested that HRMOs prioritized compliance and that having an initiative was a crucial enabling ability for HRMOs. In addition, this paper finished with a Strategic Human Resource Management Framework for SUC, which helped HRMO provide its stakeholders with superior HR services (Adrias, 2022).

The majority of schools have trouble keeping their teachers' commitments. There is a clear and present trend of private school teachers leaving to work in public schools. Furthermore, it is highly likely that the low pay and benefits, unfavorable working conditions, and low status of teachers in certain institutions contribute to this dilemma with regard to their dedication. Meanwhile, the lack of qualified and tenured instructors in public schools is brought about by the members' declining interest in the field. Public schools are negatively impacted by this widespread trend, and Calamba City's Schools Division is undoubtedly not exempt from it.

As a public school teacher who is passionate about human resources, which is an important aspect of educational administration, and with the encouragement of several fellow educators who might gain from this research, she set out to comprehend how resource

management is implemented in Calamba City Schools Division schools. Additionally, the study may offer information that might be used to develop strategic human resource plans that will benefit the organization and meet its needs.

The current study, which focused on the development of human resource management, was covered under the Educational Program Management referred to as Adoption of the Basic Education Research Agenda (2016, DepEd Order No. 39). Since teaching is the major function of educational institutions, the present study focused primarily on the role that public elementary school teachers have in delivering learning. The study evaluated the effectiveness of public elementary school teachers in Calamba City's Schools Division as well as the Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME HRM) practices in this article. This might help the study build a more robust organization, which would give workers a more fulfilling experience.

The school head, who also serves as a resource management practitioner, is expected to take the lead in encouraging teachers to aspire for a high standard of living and serve as role models by being involved in their employment concerns to provide an appropriate response to the demands and challenges related to human resources in the educational system. The report details how the school HRM system is implemented and how teachers are monitoring their employment status.

Research Questions

The study assessed the Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME HRM) practices and the performance of public elementary school teachers in the Schools Division of Calamba City. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation of PRIME HRM practices in the Division of Calamba City as assessed by the school heads and teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. recruitment, selection and placement;
 - 1.2. learning and development;
 - 1.3. performance management; and
 - 1.4. rewards and recognition?
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the school heads and teachers on the level of implementation of PRIME HRM practices?
3. What is the school performance level of public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City in terms of:
 - 3.1. access;
 - 3.2. quality; and
 - 3.3. efficiency?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of PRIME HRM practices and school performance level of public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

Methodology

This study used a quantitative research design, namely a descriptive-correlational one. Objective measurements, statistical analysis, and the collection of numerical data were the main focuses of quantitative research methodologies. Because the method looked at the link between an independent and dependent variable, it was most appropriate for this investigation. When examining the relationships between two or more random variables within the same population or between the same random variables within two different populations, correlational research proved useful. This was also in line with the study's objective, which was to ascertain how public elementary school performance was correlated with the degree of HRM practices (Adedoyin, 2020).

Results and Discussion

PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Recruitment, Selection, and Placement Fully Practiced (4.66). Furthermore, the indicator "Strategic Workforce planning system is directed to meet the present up to the long-term needs of the Agency" had the highest computed composite mean of 4.70 interpreted as Fully Practiced.

Meanwhile, the indicator "Talent attraction is done through participation in job fairs, campus recruitment, and publication in the Agency intranet" had the lowest computed composite mean of 4.60 interpreted as Fully Practice.

The Calamba City Division consistently shows its commitment to using PRIME HRM practices in the recruitment, placement, and selection procedures. To achieve this, the strategic workforce planning system is prioritized for use. School principals handle the HR responsibilities, which include directing the Promotion and Selection Board (PSB) process and leading the results deliberation, as they have the last say in matters relating to hiring, choosing, and assigning teachers to particular schools.

When employees at educational institutions, like schools, were highly skilled and competent in what they did, they could easily accomplish their goals. Supervising the school's educational organization was one of the principal's strategic duties as an education administrator (Sukawati et al., 2020).

Table 1.1. *Level of Implementation of PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City as assessed by the School Heads and Teachers in terms of Recruitment, Selection, and Placement*

Indicators in terms of Recruitment, Selection, and Placement	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
	1. Strategic Workforce planning system is directed to meet the present up to the long-term needs of the Agency.	4.85	FP	4.55	FP	4.70	
2. Human Resources Information System (HRIS) maintains data on online recruitment, selection and placement as well the profile of talents that agency hires and loses. It also generates customized reports	4.87	FP	4.51	FP	4.69	FP	2
3. A Promotion and Selection Board (PSB) is in place, with HR as lead in driving the process. It is open to partnering with external professional experts, depending on the position being considered.	4.78	FP	4.48	FP	4.63	FP	6.5
4. A well-defined Recruitment, Selection and Placement Procedures Manual with online system aligned to the Agency's strategic goals are in place.	4.83	FP	4.52	FP	4.67	FP	3.5
5. Orientation is provided to all employees on the provisions and procedures contained in the Recruitment, Selection and Placement Manual.	4.78	FP	4.53	FP	4.65	FP	5
6. Talent attraction is done through participation in job fairs, campus recruitment, and publication in the Agency intranet	4.74	FP	4.45	FP	4.60	FP	8
7. Candidate qualifications are properly matched vis-à-vis the specific or competency-based qualification standards and competency-based job description for selected positions.	4.78	FP	4.48	FP	4.63	FP	6.5
8. Comparative assessment and final evaluation is done by Line Managers and Promotion and Selection Board (PSB), with the HR Manager taking the lead in the deliberation of results making use of various competency assessment methods (simulation, in-basket, discussion, role-playing) for senior and identified key positions only, documented structured background investigation, and competency validation. Weights are assigned to personality tests and competencies.	4.83	FP	4.52	FP	4.67	FP	3.5
General Assessment	4.81	FP	4.51	FP	4.66	FP	

Legend: 4.20–5.00 Fully Practiced (FP)/Always Implemented; 3.40–4.19 Practiced (P)/Often Implemented; 2.60–3.39 Partially Practiced (PP)/Frequently Implemented; 1.80–2.59 Less Practiced (LP)/Rarely Implemented; 1.00–1.79 Not Practiced (NP)/Not Implemented

According to Naitore and Wanyoike (2019) as mentioned in Afsal et al., human resource competitive tactics that increased firm efficiency included human resource planning. Companies always sought applicants with the right mix of skills and experience. Companies with unclear HR strategy had a higher chance of failing.

Table 1.2. *Level of Implementation of PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City as assessed by the School Heads and Teachers in terms of Learning and Development*

Indicators in terms of Learning and Development	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
	1. A separate unit/group for Learning/Training Center is established, with HR as lead in driving the process of making decisions related to HRD/L&D interventions.	4.83	FP	4.54	FP	4.68	
2. HRD/L&D investment plan is set according to Agency's strategic mandate, and is approved by Agency authorities.	4.85	FP	4.53	FP	4.69	FP	7.5
3. L&D Hours are defined per employee as follows: Minimum Hours of hours per year based on the Individual Development Plan of the employees.	4.85	FP	4.54	FP	4.69	FP	7.5
4. Training and development needs identification and analysis is based on alignment between strategic organization direction with employee performance and competency gaps and career growth, and is updated every year.	4.85	FP	4.54	FP	4.70	FP	4
5. Three-year Strategic Training and Development plan is prioritized and updated on a yearly basis. The plan responds to performance and competency gaps that require training and other HRD modes / methodologies, including scholarship, integrated on-boarding, and succession planning requirements. The Agency has a written and formalized L&D plan for all core positions	4.87	FP	4.53	FP	4.70	FP	4
6. The strategic training plan provides a culture of learning that helps the organization continually improve achievement of goals and attain new possibilities and capacities.	4.85	FP	4.55	FP	4.70	FP	4
7. Training interventions are designed to support the Agency's Strategic Talent Plan, knowledge sharing, and continuous improvement	4.89	FP	4.56	FP	4.73	FP	1
8. Development of interventions is in partnership with external or foreign L&D partners geared toward interactive learning and sharing.	4.87	FP	4.54	FP	4.70	FP	4
9. HRD delivery is through the use of various HRD modes and methodologies including innovative learning methods.	4.85	FP	4.51	FP	4.68	FP	9.5
10. Management trainee or cadetship program for High Potentials is implemented.	4.87	FP	4.46	FP	4.67	FP	12
11. Established pool of internal trainers/facilitators and external or foreign L&D partners	4.85	FP	4.49	FP	4.67	FP	12

conducts training programs								
12. Training evaluation is done through Return on Investment (ROI) of L&D programs in relation to the Agency’s strategic talent plan and impact of delivery of service to the client.	4.89	FP	4.50	FP	4.70	FP	4	
13. All HR-related information is linked to Human Resources Information System (HRIS) that supports monitoring and evaluation of:	4.87	FP	4.48	FP	4.67	FP	12	
	General Assessment		4.86	FP	4.52	FP	4.69	FP

Legend: 4.20–5.00 Fully Practiced (FP)/Always Implemented; 3.40–4.19 Practiced (P)/Often Implemented; 2.60–3.39 Partially Practiced (PP)/Frequently Implemented; 1.80–2.59 Less Practiced (LP)/Rarely Implemented; 1.00–1.79 Not Practiced (NP)/Not Implemented

PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Learning and Development, were Fully Practiced (Always Implemented, 4.69). “Training interventions are designed to support the Agency’s Strategic Talent Plan, knowledge sharing, and continuous improvement”, got the highest composite mean of 4.73 interpreted as Fully Practiced. On the other hand, “Management trainee or cadetship program for High Potentials is implemented.” and “Established pool of internal trainers/facilitators and external or foreign L&D partners conducts training programs”, got the lowest composite mean of 4.67 interpreted as Fully Practiced.

This implies that the Division of Calamba City is doing its job well, and thus, empowered to implement programs that promote professional advancement and lifelong learning. It also suggests that intensive training interventions are evident in the implementation of PRIME HRM Practices in the division. If at all, the result implies that the Division of Calamba City has less priority among management trainees, and they are also less involved in foreign L&D partners in conducting training programs. This can be attributed to the availability of more viable local partners and trainers.

In the context of human resource management (HRM), learning and development (L&D) were intrinsically linked to organizational activities with the aim of improving and developing individual, group, or organizational performances. Considering the progress of technology, the efficiency of organizations, and the experiences of human resources in the workplace, learning and development (L&D) was vital (Diaz, 2022).

When staff members were extremely competent and professional in their work, schools and other educational institutions had no trouble achieving their objectives. Managing the school's educational organization was a strategic duty of the principal, an education administrator (Sukawati et al., 2020).

Table 1.3. Level of Implementation of PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City as assessed by the School Heads and Teachers in terms of Performance Management

Indicators in terms of Performance Management	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI		
1. HR leads in driving the performance management process. HR partners with Management in making decisions related to talent retention, promotion, and development	4.91	FP	4.53	FP	4.72	FP	7.5	
2. Target setting is through individual Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which are supportive of strategic Agency goals.	4.89	FP	4.55	FP	4.72	FP	7.5	
3. Core competencies for all employees are established	4.91	FP	4.57	FP	4.74	FP	4	
4. Leadership, organizational and functional competency development goals for senior managers and supervisors are present.	4.91	FP	4.57	FP	4.74	FP	4	
5. Continual coaching for results and mentoring sessions are documented.	4.85	FP	4.57	FP	4.71	FP	9.5	
6. Self-rating by employee is done on year-end performance review with competencies and development needs identified.	4.89	FP	4.58	FP	4.73	FP	6	
7. Performance Improvement Plan based on competencies is set up as needed.	4.93	FP	4.60	FP	4.77	FP	1	
8. Performance discussion is done on delivery of individual and team goals and competencies, and how these support organizational goals.	4.91	FP	4.58	FP	4.75	FP	2	
9. Establishment of Individual Development Plans for all levels is done.	4.89	FP	4.58	FP	4.74	FP	4	
10. Calibration of the application of performance standards to the value of performance ratings is done consistently throughout the Agency.	4.85	FP	4.55	FP	4.70	FP	11.5	
11. Electronic copy of interactive Performance Commitment, Evaluation, and Development Plan Forms is in use.	4.85	FP	4.57	FP	4.71	FP	9.5	
12. Link to HRIS supports monitoring and evaluation of data generated from electronic Performance Management System (PMS) to facilitate and help in decision-making.	4.85	FP	4.56	FP	4.70	FP	11.5	
	General Assessment		4.89	FP	4.57	FP	4.73	FP

Legend: 4.20–5.00 Fully Practiced (FP)/Always Implemented; 3.40–4.19 Practiced (P)/Often Implemented; 2.60–3.39 Partially Practiced (PP)/Frequently Implemented; 1.80–2.59 Less Practiced (LP)/Rarely Implemented; 1.00–1.79 Not Practiced (NP)/Not Implemented

PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Performance Management were Fully Practiced (Always Implemented, 4.73). The indicator “Performance Improvement Plan based on competencies is set up as needed” scored the highest composite mean at 4.77 interpreted as Fully Practiced/Always Implemented. In contrast, indicators “Calibration of the application of performance standards to the value of performance ratings is done consistently throughout the Agency” and “Link to HRIS supports

monitoring and evaluation of data generated from electronic Performance Management System (PMS) to facilitate and help in decision-making” scored the lowest mean of 4.70 interpreted as Fully Practiced/Always Implemented.

The result implies that the Division of Calamba City has been demonstrating a high of disposition of PRIME HRM practices performance management.

When staff members were extremely competent and professional in their work, schools and other educational institutions had no trouble achieving their objectives. Managing the school's educational organization was a strategic duty of the principal, an education administrator (Sukawati et al., 2020).

Table 1.4. *Level of Implementation of PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City as assessed by the School Heads and Teachers in terms of Rewards and Recognition*

Indicators in terms of Rewards and Recognition	School Heads		Teachers		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. Rewards and Recognition Committee engages employees and considers global practices and emerging trends in the development of programs that support the Agency strategy.	4.83	FP	4.54	FP	4.68	FP	3
2. Budget for rewards and incentives is based on savings generated from suggestions, innovations, and other cost-efficiency measures.	4.83	FP	4.47	FP	4.65	FP	4
3. Recognition is given in the form of monetary/in-kind reward or program geared toward enhancing work-life balance and employee engagement.	4.78	FP	4.42	FP	4.60	FP	5
4. Types of Programs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee Suggestion: ideas and innovations that positively affect public interest • Performance Contest: Agency achievement based on sustained effort • Desired Behavior Award: Going the extra mile • Engagement award: Work-life balance 	4.898	FP	4.53	FP	4.71	FP	2
5. Link to Human Resources Information System (HRIS) and maintains Individual historical awards data, demographics and profile of awardees, and database of recognition system	4.93	FP	4.50	FP	4.72	FP	1
General Assessment		4.85	FP	4.49	FP	4.67	FP

Legend: 4.20–5.00 Fully Practiced (FP)/Always Implemented; 3.40–4.19 Practiced (P)/Often Implemented; 2.60–3.39 Partially Practiced (PP)/Frequently Implemented; 1.80–2.59 Less Practiced (LP)/Rarely Implemented; 1.00–1.79 Not Practiced (NP)/Not Implemented

PRIME HRM Practices in the Division of Calamba City in terms of PRIME HRM Practices in terms of Rewards and Recognition were Fully Practiced (Always Implemented, 4.67). The indicator “Link to Human Resources Information System (HRIS) and maintains individual historical awards data, demographics and profile of awardees, and database of recognition system” scored the highest composite mean of 4.71 interpreted as Fully Practiced/Always Implemented. In the meantime, “Recognition is given in the form of monetary/in-kind reward or program geared toward enhancing work-life balance and employee engagement” yielded the lowest composite mean of 4.60 interpreted as Fully Practiced/Always Implemented.

It implies that the Division of Calamba City has a good information system design that links all the information that is accessible to all concerns. The School Heads are quite higher than teachers because they deal with all the processes and procedures rewards and recognition while the teachers are focused more on their duties and assigned functions.

Within the See et al. (2020) investigation, financial incentives were used for decades in an attempt to entice more graduates to pursue careers as teachers. While there was evidence for their potential benefits, nothing suggested that they would "solve" the long-term recruitment issues that the US and similar countries were currently confronting. Given that the attractiveness was obviously transient, we wondered, for example, if offering financial incentives was always the best way to improve recruiting. Financial incentives, however, might have been a helpful tactic to attract teachers to challenging schools or regions and to augment the pool of available shortage subject instructors.

There was a significant difference in the assessment of the school heads and teachers on the level of implementation of PRIME HRM practices. The generated computed probability values of Recruitment, Selection and Placement, Learning and Development, Performance Management, and Rewards and Recognition were .000 respectively which was less than the level of significance at 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

It implies that, given that the implementing agencies follow uniform regulations enforced by the government, it is logical to believe that educators and administrators will view PRIME HRM practices in a similar light. The differences in their judgments can be explained by the School Head's executive authority to carry out the policies and procedures of the institution.

In addition, the School Head manages the institution's human resources. Because of this, they have gained more experience and insight from their roles as HR managers. They are therefore more equipped to decide on and carry out human resource procedures at the school level.

Table 2. *Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the School Heads and Teachers on the Level of Implementation of PRIME HRM Practices*

Sub-variables		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F Ratio	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Recruitment, Selection and Placement	Between Groups	3.633	1	3.633	14.179	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	89.672	350	.256				
	Total	93.305	351					
Learning and Development	Between Groups	4.586	1	4.586	18.329	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	87.579	350	.250				
	Total	92.165	351					
Performance Management	Between Groups	4.116	1	4.116	17.537	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	82.138	350	.235				
	Total	86.254	351					
Rewards and Recognition	Between Groups	5.202	1	5.202	19.329	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	94.193	350	.269				
	Total	99.395	351					

The results demonstrated the critical role that principal leadership played in formulating plans and directives that promoted the enhancement of educational quality. Principals were required to be highly committed to raising the standard of instruction in their institutions and possessed the ability to provide workable solutions. Principals also overcame a number of obstacles and difficulties when putting quality improvement plans into practice, including a shortage of time, limited resources, and reluctance to change on the part of some instructors. Effective resource management, good staff communication, and efficient administrative work management were all necessary for principals. The outcomes also showed a link between better instruction and principal leadership. To achieve quality improvement, teachers, students, and other stakeholders were inspired to collaborate by transformational principal leadership. This was especially true if the principal effectively communicated a clear vision, encouraged creativity in the classroom, and established a welcoming and cooperative school environment (Siregar, 2024).

Table 3.1. *School Performance Level of Public Elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Access*

Indicators	Rating & Equivalent	F	%
High	at least 7% increase	11	23.91%
Average	At least 5% increase	16	34.78%
Marginal	At least 3% increase	19	41.30%
	Total	46	100%
	Average Rating	3.93%	

The school performance of public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Access was 3.93%. Furthermore, nineteen (19) out of 46 schools, or 41.30% garnered high performance, 16, or 34.78% garnered average performance, while 11 out of 46, or 23.91% schools performed high.

The findings imply that most public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City are at the borderline of showing no improvement in school access. This is attributed to the overwhelming increase in enrollment in public schools during the pandemic. This increase is due to the mass transfers of students from private schools to public schools for practical and economic reasons. However, after the pandemic and as schools return to face-to-face classes, those students are transferring back to private schools, which eventually decreases enrollment in public schools.

Access to education provided education to everyone who was eligible for it, whereas equity in access to education referred to ensuring that every member of society had equal access to the educational opportunities provided by the community (Owan et al., 2019). According to Babalola et al. (as cited by Owan et al., 2019), eliminating any obstacles that might have prevented someone from taking advantage of the educational opportunities that were accessible was what was meant by equality in access to education. This made high-quality education accessible to everyone who was motivated and had the right to an education.

The school performance of public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Quality was 5.07% interpreted as Average. Furthermore, twenty-three (23) out of 46 schools, or 50% garnered high performance, 10, or 21.74% garnered average performance, while 13 out of 46, or 28.26% schools performed high.

Table 3.2. *School Performance Level of Public Elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Quality*

Indicators	Rating & Equivalent	F	%
High	at least 7% increase	23	50%
Average	At least 5% increase	10	21.74%
Marginal	At least 3% increase	13	28.26%
	Total	46	100%
	Average Rating	5.07%	

Results show that some schools in the Division of Calamba City maintain only an average level of quality, which reflects on the academic performance of the learners and their obtained level of performance in local and national examinations. Many efforts are made, but the same is regarded in terms of their performance.

At all levels of education, raising the standard of instructional tactics and teaching-learning approaches was of utmost importance. Sufficient focus was also placed on improving the quality of other environmental circumstances. These included the environment in general, technology, tools, supplies, infrastructure, and facilities. In conclusion, it could be claimed that in order to consistently improve the efficacy and standard of the educational system, individuals had to spread awareness and put plans and strategies into action (Kapur, 2019).

The school performance of public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City in terms of drop-out rate was 1.30%. Furthermore, one or 2.17% garnered 7.06% decreased in drop-out rate; seven schools or 15.22% had at least a 4% decrease in drop-out; and 38 or 82.61% had at least a 2% decrease in their drop-out rate.

Table 3.3. School Performance Level of Public Elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City in terms of Efficiency

Indicators	Rating & Equivalent	F	%
Drop-out Rate			
High	at least 7.06% decrease	1	2.17%
Average	At least 4% decrease	7	15.22%
Marginal	At least 2% decrease	38	82.61%
	Total	46	100%
	Average Rating	1.30%	
Completion Rate			
High	at least 10% increase or at least 95%	46	100%
Average	At least 7% increase	0	0%
Marginal	At least 5% increase	0	0%
	Total	46	100%
	Average Rating	98.86%	
Cohort Survival Rate			
High	at least 10% increase or at least 95% CSR	46	100%
Average	At least 7% increase	0	0%
Marginal	At least 5% increase	0	0%
	Total	46	46
	Average Rating	98.83%	

In terms of completion rate, the average rating was 98.86%. The data also expressed that 46 (100%) public elementary schools achieved at least 10% increase or at least 95% completion rate. Meanwhile, the cohort survival rate was 98.83%. All the schools achieved at least 10% or at least 95% cohort survival rate.

The results demonstrate that public elementary schools in Calamba City's Division struggle to continuously lower their dropout rates until they reach zero. Records indicate that the cohort survival rate and school completion performance metrics are superior despite numerous attempts. The principals give several explanations for their approach to this challenge. To rekindle students' passion in education, they implement policies and programs. The catch-up program is in place.

Although not all schools implement student monitoring, it is discovered that some do so to raise the percentage of children who participate. New students are made to feel welcome and included in a range of participatory activities. Different solutions are suggested by the school heads' assessments of the Schools Division Office since the dropout rates at certain of their schools are lower than those at other schools.

It was shown that shared leadership and a cooperative approach between leaders and teachers—particularly in the area of instructional improvement—were essential elements of long-term school growth that improved student performance (Lee & Louis, 2019).

There was no significant relationship between the level of implementation of PRIME HRM practices and the school performance level of public elementary schools in the Division of Calamba City. The r values ranging from .047 to .180 were interpreted as with negligible correlation as to correlate PRIME HRM practices and school performance level. The computed probability values of .235 to .756 were greater than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

It can be concluded that the increase or decrease in public elementary schools' performance cannot be connected to the implementation of PRIME HRM practices. This can be attributed to the fact that the direction of PRIME HRM practices focused specifically on the school staff and workforce. This could mean that PRIME HRM practices have a huge and positive impact on the work performance of the school heads and teachers which eventually reflects the school's level of access, quality, and efficiency.

To ensure that objectives were effectively reached, a high value was placed on the performance of educators. Any problems that arose throughout the procedure were resolved right away. The principal and other authorized parties regularly reviewed every facet of school

resource management, including teacher performance, from planning to monitoring and assessment. (Wulandari et al., 2020).

Table 4. *Test of Significant Relationship between the Implementation of PRIME HRM Practices and the Public Elementary Schools Performance Level*

<i>PRIME HRM practices</i>	<i>school performance level</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Recruitment, Selection and Placement	Access	.180	.232	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Quality	.082	.586	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Efficiency	.067	.660	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Learning and Development	Access	.114	.451	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Quality	.121	.424	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Efficiency	.056	.713	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Performance Management	Access	.140	.352	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Quality	.047	.756	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Efficiency	.057	.705	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Rewards and Recognition	Access	.134	.375	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Quality	.109	.470	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Efficiency	.054	.722	Not Significant	Accept Ho

**Significant at the level 0.01

*Significant at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn, and, offers recommendations as follows:

That the school heads have the final say in decisions about hiring, selecting, and assigning teachers to specific schools. School administrators oversee HR duties, which include managing the Promotion and Selection Board (PSB) procedure and spearheading outcomes discussions. Meanwhile, the Division of Calamba City is less active in providing training programs with overseas/foreign L&D partners and receives lower priority from management trainees. This demonstrates the high degree of disposition towards PRIME HRM practices in performance management that the Division of Calamba City exhibits, as noted by School Heads and Teachers. Moreover, teachers focus more on their jobs and designated roles, while school heads handle all procedures, awards, and recognition. For this reason, school heads hold a higher position than their teachers. Hence, to ensure that human resource management procedures in the educational system will continue, the necessity to implement PRIME-HRM policies in the schools division office may be regularly observed. Furthermore, a comprehensive evaluation and modification of the policy regarding awards and recognition are required.

That the implementing agencies follow uniform regulations enforced by the government; thus, educators and administrators view PRIME HRM practices in a similar light. The differences in their judgments can be explained by the School Head's executive authority to carry out the policies and procedures of the institution. Additionally, the School Head manages the institution's human resources, gaining more experience and insight from their roles as HR managers. Therefore, they are more equipped to decide on and carry out human resource procedures at the school level. The heads of the schools may try to improve communication about the PRIME-HRM processes and procedures by holding talks or providing in-school instruction. To support academic achievement, the head of the school may provide mentorship to all those involved in developing new ideas and enhancements—often referred to as "innovations." The conduct of school-based training and LAC sessions may be utilized to fully explain the PRIME-HRM concept.

That the majority of Calamba City's public elementary schools are on the verge of not improving student access. This is explained by the dramatic spike in public school enrollment that occurred during the epidemic. The large exodus of children from private to public schools for pragmatic and financial reasons caused this growth. However, once the epidemic ends and classrooms resume in person, these students move back to private institutions, resulting in a decline in public school enrollment. The findings indicate that several schools within the Calamba City Division have only maintained an average quality standard, impacting students' academic achievement and their performance in regional and national exams. Despite efforts to improve, performance did not increase compared to current achievements. Thus, the creation of a comprehensive technical assistance plan by the Schools Division Office is strongly advised to support various schools in achieving or sustaining school access, quality, and efficiency.

That the increase or decrease in public elementary schools' performance cannot be directly connected to the implementation of PRIME HRM practices. This is because PRIME HRM practices specifically focus on the school staff and workforce. However, PRIME HRM practices have a significant and positive impact on the work performance of school heads and teachers, eventually reflecting the school's level of access, quality, and efficiency. In line with this, all the educators and administrators need to work in coordination and integration with each other to enhance the school's access, quality, and efficiency. Human resource management needs to match teachers' expectations for peak performance if it is to have a meaningful impact on students' academic performance. In order to improve their professional lives, teachers and other school employees should attend trainings provided by schools, divisions, and higher education institutions. Furthermore, the accomplishment of an educational institution's vision and objectives is contingent upon its capacity to effectively oversee and enable its human resources, particularly with regard to the principal's human resource management.

That the proposed action plan is necessary to enhance the Implementation of PRIME HRM practices in the Division of Calamba City.

It may be implemented since it aims to improve the division of Calamba City's application of PRIME HRM principles.

Research on the connection between PRIME HRM practices and academic achievement—especially in terms of accessibility, effectiveness, and quality—is crucial. Therefore, further qualitative research is required to investigate HRM practices that support academic achievement.

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